

Detecting Images Generated by Diffusers

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9 ABSTRACT

10 In recent years, the field of artificial intelligence has witnessed a remarkable surge in the generation of
11 synthetic images, driven by advancements in deep learning techniques. These synthetic images, often
12 created through complex algorithms, closely mimic real photographs, blurring the lines between reality
13 and artificiality. This proliferation of synthetic visuals presents a pressing challenge: how to accurately
14 and reliably distinguish between genuine and generated images. This paper, in particular, explores the
15 task of detecting images generated by text-to-image diffusion models, highlighting the challenges and
16 peculiarities of this field. To evaluate this, we consider images generated from captions in the MSCOCO
17 and Wikimedia datasets using two state-of-the-art models: Stable Diffusion and GLIDE. Our experiments
18 show that it is possible to detect the generated images using simple Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs),
19 starting from features extracted by CLIP or RoBERTa, or using traditional Convolutional Neural Networks
20 (CNNs). These latter models achieve remarkable performances in particular when pretrained on large
21 datasets. We also observe that models trained on images generated by Stable Diffusion can occasionally
22 detect images generated by GLIDE, but only on the MSCOCO dataset. However, the reverse is not true.
23 Lastly, we find that incorporating the associated textual information with the images in some cases can
24 lead to a better generalization capability, especially if textual features are closely related to visual ones.
25 We also discovered that the type of subject depicted in the image can significantly impact performance.
26 This work provides insights into the feasibility of detecting generated images and has implications for
27 security and privacy concerns in real-world applications. The code to reproduce our results is available
28 at: <https://github.com/davide-coccomini/Detecting-Images-Generated-by-Diffusers>.

29 1 INTRODUCTION

30 The rapid progression of synthetic image generation techniques, notably through the advent of Generative
31 Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Diffusion Models, has ushered in an era where artificial images
32 closely resemble their real counterparts. While these advancements hold immense potential for creative
33 applications, they have also raised significant concerns regarding their misuse, particularly in the form of
34 deepfakes and the spread of misinformation. These manipulated contents can indeed be used to distort
35 reality, damage the reputation of people, and irretrievably ruin their lives.

36 To mitigate these concerns, it is crucial to develop robust techniques for detecting synthetic images
37 and distinguishing them from pristine content. The ability to detect synthetic images is essential for
38 maintaining the integrity of information and for protecting individuals from the malicious use of these
39 manipulated media. The explosion of recent text-to-image methods such as Stable Diffusion (Rombach
40 et al., 2022) and their easy access to the general public is leading society towards a point where a good
41 deal of online content is synthetic and where the line between reality and fiction will no longer be so clear.

42 In this paper, we present an analysis of peculiarities and challenges in the field of synthetic image
43 detection, considering classifications based on the image itself and the text associated with it and used to
44 describe or generate it. To explore the field of synthetic image detection, we constructed two datasets
45 based on different sets of captions and pristine images. We consider two generators, namely Stable
46 Diffusion and GLIDE to construct these datasets. We subsequently trained several binary classifiers based
47 on various deep-learning architectures, also introducing some multimodal strategies exploiting features

48 extracted from both images and associated texts. We also analyzed the peculiarities of images, such as the
49 kind of object depicted in the scene, and texts, such as linguistic features, that can lead to a more or less
50 credible image that is difficult to identify. Throughout this analysis, we have been able to highlight which
51 conditions can lead to a better synthetic image and which ones do not influence the generation process. In
52 general, we try to answer the following research questions:

- 53 • Is there a generalization problem similar to what we see in the traditional deepfake detection field?
- 54 • What is the impact of models' pretraining on synthetic image detection?
- 55 • Can the combination of visual and textual features conduct an improvement in deepfake detection?
- 56 • What are the specific visual and textual characteristics that contribute to the credibility of synthetic
57 images?

58 Portions of this text were previously published as part of a preprint (Coccomini et al., 2023b).

59 **2 RELATED WORKS**

60 **2.1 Images Generation**

61 One of the earliest GAN-based methods for synthetic image generation was introduced in (Goodfellow
62 et al., 2014). Their model consisted of a generator network that synthesized images and a discriminator
63 network that learned to distinguish between real and synthetic images. They have been used for several
64 tasks like face synthesis (Ruiz et al., 2020; Mokhayeri et al., 2019), style transfer (Xu et al., 2021) and
65 super-resolution (Ledig et al., 2017). Impressive results have been achieved in (Karras et al., 2020) where
66 the authors proposed style-based GAN architecture (StyleGAN), capable of generating more credible
67 images. Several variations of GAN architecture have been designed over the years, for example, the
68 CycleGAN proposed in (Zhu et al., 2017). This architecture can perform the task of image-to-image
69 translation, optimizing a cycle loss and also allowing the revert of the mapping process. GAN architecture
70 has also been used for the task of text-to-image translation in which a text describing a context is converted
71 into an image. In particular, in (Qiao et al., 2019) the MirrorGAN is proposed. The authors exploit the
72 concept of re-description in the sense that the image generated starting from a text, should be describable
73 by another text which is similar to the source one. So, the model needs to learn to generate images whose
74 re-description matches as much as possible with the requested one. Recently a novel architecture was
75 introduced to perform similar tasks, namely Diffusion Models. These models generate images by refining
76 an initial noise vector through multiple diffusion steps. For text-to-image generation, a given text is
77 encoded into a latent vector used as the initial noise. Some of these models obtained unprecedented results
78 such as DALL-E (Ramesh et al., 2021), GLIDE (Nichol et al., 2022) and Stable Diffusion (Rombach
79 et al., 2022). These models have a high control of image generation, allowing the users to create very
80 credible images with a high level of detail.

81 **2.2 Synthetic Images Detection**

82 The growing credibility and diffusion of generated images raised some concerns in the research community,
83 which tried to develop methods capable of effectively distinguishing synthetic content from pristine one.
84 For a long time, the main efforts were focused on traditional deepfakes referring to face manipulation,
85 with a lot of works proposed trying to detect them (Coccomini et al., 2022c; Zheng et al., 2021; Coccomini
86 et al., 2022a; Guarnera et al., 2022; Coccomini et al., 2023a; Baxevanakis et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020;
87 Coccomini et al., 2022b; Caldelli et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022; Cozzolino et al., 2020). Otherwise,
88 with the recent advancement of generation techniques, attention has also been posed to generic-generated
89 content without a fundamental focus on images depicting humans. For example, in (Sha et al., 2022)
90 the authors tried to detect images generated by some diffusion models in two setups, image-only and
91 image+text being capable of effectively distinguishing between real and generated images. In (Corvi
92 et al., 2022), the researchers tried to train some binary classifiers to distinguish images generated by
93 diffusion models and GAN models. The results highlighted how it is pretty feasible to detect images
94 when the generated method is used in the training set while there is a huge generalization problem.
95 This behaviour resides in what was also observed by (Bammey, 2024) which confirmed the presence of
96 specific artifacts for each diffusion model introduced in the frequency domain. These are memorized
97 by detectors that can be very effective in training methods but little in classifying images generated

Figure 1. The two different network setups are shown in the figure. On the left is the Image-Only Setup in which only the image under consideration is used as input to the network while ignoring its associated caption. This setup is used for some MLPs and the two convolutional networks under consideration. On the right, on the other hand, the Image+Text Setup is presented in which the features obtained from the image are concatenated with those obtained from the caption, both extracted via CLIP or using a RoBERTa model for the textual features and given as input to the network.

98 by novel techniques. The specific attributes introduced by diffusion-based generators have been also
 99 exploited in (Ma et al., 2023) where the authors proposed SeDID, an effective combination of statistical
 100 and neural network-based approach to catch them. Indeed, the classifiers seem to learn some kind of trace
 101 specific for each generator, and so are pretty limited when tested on images generated with other methods.
 102 Similar work has recently been done in (Amoroso et al., 2023) presenting a novel synthetic dataset,
 103 namely COCOFake, and highlighting the presence of common low-level cues in images generated by
 104 state-of-the-art diffusion models. Although many previous works have explored the problem of synthetic
 105 image detection, in this paper we aim to conduct a deeper analysis of the impact of the various aspects that
 106 influence this task. In particular, we will explore the role of the subjects depicted in the images on a more
 107 or less credible image as well as the influence of the linguistic structure of the captions associated with
 108 them. We will then analyze the impact of the architecture choice and the role of pretraining and different
 109 feature extraction backbones, trying to highlight their peculiarities, advantages and disadvantages.

110 3 EXPERIMENTS

111 In this section, we explain all the experiments conducted and the details to reproduce them.

112 3.1 Classifiers

113 As presented in Figure 1, we conducted our experiments in two main setups: image-only and text+image.
 114 In the first case, classification is done by using only the features extracted from the image. For this purpose,
 115 we selected some simple Deep Learning architectures to use as binary classifiers (real or generated images).
 116 In particular, the first model used is a simple MLP that takes as input the features extracted from the
 117 image by CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) encoders. CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training) is a
 118 neural network model that learns to associate natural language descriptions with images. For that reason
 119 it extracts very correlated textual and visual features. CLIP can use both ResNet50 (He et al., 2016) and
 120 Vision Transformer (ViT) (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020) features to represent the images it processes. The
 121 second category of trained models is standard Convolutional Neural Networks widely used in Computer
 122 Vision i.e., Resnet50 and XceptionNet (Chollet, 2017), both pretrained for image classification on the
 123 ImageNet dataset (Deng et al., 2009).

124 We extended the CLIP-based classifier from the previous setup by also using the text encoder provided
 125 by the architecture to extract features from the caption associated with the image. These textual features
 126 are combined with the visual features and given as input to the MLP for classification. Some experiments
 127 have been also done using the textual features extracted using a RoBERTa model (Liu et al., 2019),
 128 replacing the CLIP text encoder. RoBERTa is a pre-trained natural language processing model based on
 129 transformer architecture, designed to understand and generate human-like text by learning contextual
 130 relationships in large datasets. The features extracted with this method could be richer in linguistic
 131 information compared with CLIP textual features due to the different nature of the task the model is
 132 trained on. On the other hand, the CLIP textual features should be easier to correlate with visual features

Figure 2. An example of a caption associated with an image from the MSCOCO dataset given as input to Stable Diffusion and GLIDE to generate two additional images is shown in the figure.

	Pristine Source	Generation Method	Categorized
Set 1	MSCOCO	Stable Diffusion	×
Set 2	MSCOCO	GLIDE	×
Set 3	Wikimedia	Stable Diffusion	✓
Set 4	Wikimedia	GLIDE	✓

Table 1. Summary of the constructed datasets indicating the source of pristine images and the technique of image generation starting from their captions. The "categorized" column indicates if information about the category of the images is available.

133 to find inconsistencies between the caption and the image. The visual features remain extracted through
 134 the CLIP model also when the RoBERTa text-encoder is exploited.

135 In both setups, the MLP structure is adapted to the features' shape based on the model used for the
 136 extraction, while the other layers remain the same for all the experiments. In particular, the model is
 137 composed of one input layer, two hidden layers, and one output layer. All models used in the experiments
 138 have a similar number of parameters to allow for a fair comparison.

139 3.2 Dataset

140 To validate the ability of a classifier to effectively identify images generated from text, we considered
 141 two starting datasets, namely MSCOCO (Lin et al., 2014) composed by over 330,000 English captioned
 142 images and Wikimedia Image-Caption Matching dataset¹ based on Wikipedia Image Text Dataset (WIT)
 143 (Srinivasan et al., 2021) and contains 37.6 million entity-rich image-text examples with 11.5 million
 144 unique images across 108 Wikipedia languages. Both of these datasets consist of images from many
 145 different contexts and each of them is associated with a caption describing it as shown in Figure 2. For
 146 each of the two datasets, 6,000 images randomly sampled from the training set, and a further 6,000 images
 147 were generated using two text-to-image methods, namely Stable Diffusion v1.4 or GLIDE. Therefore, in
 148 the constructed sets, for each caption sampled from the source dataset there is one pristine and one fake
 149 image generated using a text-to-image model. The same was done with 1,500 images from the validation
 150 set and another 6,000 from the test set. Therefore, all models were trained on a training set consisting
 151 of 12,000 images, half of which were generated by Stable Diffusion, and the same have been done with
 152 another training set with images generated by GLIDE. We then constructed four different sets, each one
 153 composed of a total of 27,000 images, split in train/validation/test based on the annotations provided by
 154 the datasets' authors. To perform a more detailed analysis of the behaviour of the classifiers considered,
 155 the images from the Wikimedia dataset and the corresponding generated images were categorized based
 156 on the Wikipedia ontologies available online. An overview of the constructed datasets is shown in Table 1
 157 and the code to reproduce them is available at (Coccomini et al., 2024).

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/c/wikipedia-image-caption/overview>

Model	Dataset	Mode	Features	Accuracy \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Params	Pretrain
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Image Only	CLIP-VIT	79.5	88.8	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-VIT	78.5	88.8	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-VIT	75.4	89.1	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Image Only	CLIP-R50	67.5	75.0	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	66.5	74.2	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	59.3	75.0	23M	N/A
XceptionNet	MSCOCO	Image Only	XceptionNet	90.6	96.6	20M	N/A
XceptionNet	MSCOCO	Image Only	XceptionNet	94.6	98.9	20M	ImageNet
Resnet50	MSCOCO	Image Only	Resnet50	87.8	94.3	23M	N/A
Resnet50	MSCOCO	Image Only	Resnet50	97.1	99.6	23M	ImageNet
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Image Only	CLIP-VIT	72.8	81.4	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-VIT	73.1	80.8	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-VIT	58.1	81.6	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Image Only	CLIP-R50	65.9	74.2	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	64.5	73.5	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	67.7	74.5	23M	N/A
XceptionNet	Wikipedia	Image Only	XceptionNet	82.3	91.2	20M	N/A
XceptionNet	Wikipedia	Image Only	XceptionNet	90.7	97.1	20M	ImageNet
Resnet50	Wikipedia	Image Only	Resnet50	78.1	87.8	23M	N/A
Resnet50	Wikipedia	Image Only	Resnet50	94.5	98.1	23M	ImageNet

Table 2. Results on the test set of the various classifiers trained and tested on real images and images generated with Stable Diffusion. For each row, the dataset considered, training mode used, features extracted via CLIP or convolutional layers, accuracy and AUC, number of model parameters, and whether pretraining was used are indicated.

3.3 Training Setup

The classifiers considered were simple Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs), which take visual and textual features from CLIP, RoBERTa or widely used convolutional networks, in particular, ResNet50 and XceptionNet. The former are trained from scratch, while the convolutional networks are considered also in the case of ImageNet pretraining. All models are trained with a learning rate of 0.1, decreasing to 0.001, for up to 270 epochs on an NVIDIA A100. MLPs are trained in two possible setups: image-only and text+image. CLIP-extracted features are extracted from the image in both the setups while in the text+image context, the captions’ features are obtained through CLIP text-encoder or using RoBERTa. In the text+image setup, the features are concatenated before being given as input to the model as shown in Figure 1, which is then able to see both the textual and visual components in a single vector. The encoders used in all these experiments are frozen and just used for feature extraction. Instead, the CNNs considered are trained exclusively in image-only mode, and the features used for classification are those resulting from the convolutional layers of the considered architecture. To explore the possibility of training also the backbone, in this case, we fine-tuned the whole architecture.

4 RESULTS

In this section, we show the results obtained in two main contexts, intra-method and cross-method.

4.1 In-Method Classification

Table 2 shows the performances, in terms of accuracy and AUC, of the classifiers considered when trained and tested with real images and images generated by Stable Diffusion, according to the setup illustrated above. As can be seen from the results, the pretrained Resnet50 and XceptionNet exhibit remarkable capabilities in identifying generated images by acting as almost perfect detectors. However, the same models demonstrate lower accuracy in classification in the absence of pretraining, although remaining vastly more effective than MLP-based classifiers. Indeed, on the other hand, MLPs achieve satisfactory results especially when CLIP visual features extracted via a Vision Transformer are used, without the use of pretrain on large datasets. Another element that greatly influences the result, especially for MLPs is certainly the dataset, images from Wikimedia seem to be more difficult to distinguish. This probably results from the wide variety of images and contexts in this dataset, however, even in this case the models manage to achieve good levels of accuracy.

Model	Dataset	Mode	Features	Accuracy \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Params	Pretrain
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Image Only	CLIP-ViT	95.8	99.2	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-ViT	95.8	99.2	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-ViT	96.3	99.2	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Image Only	CLIP-R50	79.0	87.4	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	78.0	86.4	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	MSCOCO	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	77.4	87.1	23M	N/A
XceptionNet	MSCOCO	Image Only	XceptionNet	99.3	99.9	20M	N/A
XceptionNet	MSCOCO	Image Only	XceptionNet	99.2	99.9	20M	ImageNet
Resnet50	MSCOCO	Image Only	Resnet50	80.0	93.1	23M	N/A
Resnet50	MSCOCO	Image Only	Resnet50	99.3	99.9	23M	ImageNet
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Image Only	CLIP-ViT	93.7	98.4	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-ViT	94.3	98.4	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-ViT	93.5	98.4	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Image Only	CLIP-R50	77.1	85.2	23M	N/A
MLP-Base	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	75.5	84.5	23M	N/A
MLP-RoBERTa	Wikipedia	Text+Image	CLIP-R50	76.4	84.8	23M	N/A
XceptionNet	Wikipedia	Image Only	XceptionNet	98.7	99.8	20M	N/A
XceptionNet	Wikipedia	Image Only	XceptionNet	98.9	99.9	20M	ImageNet
Resnet50	Wikipedia	Image Only	Resnet50	74.3	88.4	23M	N/A
Resnet50	Wikipedia	Image Only	Resnet50	99.5	99.9	23M	ImageNet

Table 3. Results on the test set of the various classifiers trained and tested on real images and images generated with GLIDE. For each row, the dataset considered, training mode used, features extracted via CLIP or convolutional layers, accuracy and AUC, number of model parameters, and whether pretraining was used are indicated.

186 As shown instead in Table 3, the images generated via GLIDE seem to be much easier to detect
187 on both datasets, even without the use of pretraining. The MLP with CLIP-ViT features is by far the
188 best MLP setup. Pretrained XceptionNet and Resnet50 perform almost perfectly with accuracies around
189 99%. The absence of pretraining in this case is more impactful on the Resnet50 than on the XceptionNet.
190 The latter scores a very good performance even without pretraining probably exploiting some particular
191 artifacts introduced by GLIDE. As can be seen in Figure 3, the images generated by GLIDE appear to
192 be more artefactual and bogus than those generated by Stable Diffusion from the same caption, which
193 obtains more credible results. Just as the latter are more difficult to identify with the naked eye, the models
194 experience similar difficulties.

195 In many experiments, using RoBERTa’s textual features instead of the ones extracted through the
196 CLIP text encoder led to decreased performances. This means that the textual features extracted using the
197 CLIP encoder are more expressive and clear in combination with the visual ones allowing the classifier to
198 reach higher performances in the majority of setups.

199 4.2 Cross-Method Classification

200 The trained models have shown a great ability to identify images generated by text-to-image systems.
201 However, in this section, we want to find out whether they can generalize the concept of generated
202 images to such an extent that they can identify images created with different generators. Indeed, many
203 text-to-image systems are available, and a real-world deployed model should be able to identify generated
204 images regardless of the method used. The risk is in fact that these classifiers learn to distinguish some sort
205 of trace, noise or imprint left by the generator instead of focusing on more general, high-level anomalies
206 or inconsistencies, thus rendering them useless in the real world. To validate this, we tried training models
207 on real images and images generated with Stable Diffusion and tested them on images generated with
208 GLIDE, and vice versa.

209 In Table 4 we report the results of the same models evaluated in Section 4.1 in a cross-forgery context.
210 The accuracy figures in this more realistic setup are sensibly lower and the MLP models using ViT features
211 close the gap concerning CNNs. Two models stand out in terms of accuracy and AUC, namely the MLP
212 trained in the image+text setup using CLIP textual features and the Resnet50. The latter succeeds in
213 generalizing better than other models but only when pretrained, highlighting how pretraining models on
214 large datasets can be of crucial help in improving generalization. The MLP-based detector trained on the
215 image+text setup has a substantial positive difference from the same model trained in the image-only one.

Figure 3. Comparison between GLIDE and Stable Diffusion generated images from the same caption.

Model	Training Method	Testing Method	Mode	Features	Accuracy \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Pretrain
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	CLIP-R50	50.8	50.3	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	49.9	50.9	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	50.4	50.8	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	CLIP-VIT	64.9	75.7	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	69.7	76.2	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	60.9	75.3	N/A
XceptionNet	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	XceptionNet	53.1	57.6	N/A
XceptionNet	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	XceptionNet	58.9	76.1	ImageNet
Resnet50	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	Resnet50	53.8	59.3	N/A
Resnet50	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	Resnet50	61.4	86.1	ImageNet
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	CLIP-R50	51.5	51.7	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	50.6	51.1	N/A
MLP-Roberta	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	51.4	51.7	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	CLIP-VIT	48.8	45.9	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	52.3	61.5	N/A
MLP-Roberta	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	51.1	60.9	N/A
XceptionNet	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	XceptionNet	50.0	67.5	N/A
XceptionNet	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	XceptionNet	50.2	73.5	ImageNet
Resnet50	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	Resnet50	48.9	47.7	N/A
Resnet50	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	Resnet50	50.2	64.6	ImageNet

Table 4. Results obtained by the considered classifiers trained on real images and generated with Stable Diffusion and then tested on real images and generated with GLIDE, and vice versa on the MSCOCO dataset.

216 Since the model can no longer fully exploit visual information, not having had the opportunity to learn
 217 artifacts from images generated by other methods, it exploits the linguistic information contained in the
 218 caption. In particular, the model could notice the inconsistencies between what is described in the caption
 219 and what is represented in the images. In fact, both the language features extracted using RoBERTa
 220 and those obtained through CLIP lead to improved performance. The latter, however, are even more
 221 effective because they are designed to relate what is described in the caption and what is represented in
 222 the image, thus making it easier for the model to find inconsistencies. A similar trend can be observed in
 223 the case of models trained with images generated using GLIDE and tested with images obtained through
 224 Stable Diffusion. In this case, the classification is more complex, in fact the images generated with Stable
 225 Diffusion are more challenging and training on GLIDE-generated images is not enough for the model to
 226 detect them. Nevertheless, again the introduction of textual features leads to improved performance.

227 The same experiments were conducted on Wikimedia datasets as illustrated in Table 5. In this context,
 228 the difficulties that the models had already encountered in the previous experiments become even more
 229 evident and stem probably from the greater challenge of the dataset. As it is much more varied than
 230 MSCOCO, it makes generalization more difficult, as the models have to learn to distinguish between
 231 images generated from very varied contexts. Practically no model manages to exceed the accuracy of

Model	Training Method	Testing Method	Mode	Features	Accuracy \uparrow	AUC \uparrow	Pretrain
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	CLIP-R50	36.4	44.8	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	36.7	45.7	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	41.0	36.2	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	CLIP-VIT	46.2	40.5	N/A
MLP-Base	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	43.4	34.4	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	49.1	38.2	N/A
XceptionNet	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	XceptionNet	46.2	37.7	N/A
XceptionNet	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	XceptionNet	48.9	48.8	ImageNet
Resnet50	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	Resnet50	47.6	42.8	N/A
Resnet50	Stable Diffusion	GLIDE	Image-Only	Resnet50	50.9	55.0	ImageNet
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	CLIP-R50	45.6	39.9	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	39.4	45.8	N/A
MLP-Roberta	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	45.8	39.8	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	CLIP-VIT	48.8	45.9	N/A
MLP-Base	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	48.0	45.8	N/A
MLP-Roberta	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	48.8	45.6	N/A
XceptionNet	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	XceptionNet	50.9	49.6	N/A
XceptionNet	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	XceptionNet	49.3	49.6	ImageNet
Resnet50	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	Resnet50	42.7	39.7	N/A
Resnet50	GLIDE	Stable Diffusion	Image-Only	Resnet50	49.2	53.7	ImageNet

Table 5. Results obtained by the considered classifiers trained on real images and generated with Stable Diffusion and then tested on real images and generated with GLIDE, and vice versa on the Wikimedia dataset.

Model	Mode	Features	Stable Diffusion				GLIDE				Pretrain
			Animated		Inanimate		Animated		Inanimate		
			FN \downarrow	FP \downarrow	FN \downarrow	FP \downarrow	FN \downarrow	FP \downarrow	FN \downarrow	FP \downarrow	
MLP-Base	Image-Only	CLIP-R50	26.4	8.3	31.0	16.4	15.9	8.3	20.6	16.1	N/A
MLP-Base	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	28.6	7.6	35.0	15.7	17.6	7.5	23.3	15.7	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Image+Text	CLIP-R50	12.6	34.0	16.6	31.0	16.7	8.4	21.4	15.8	N/A
MLP-Base	Image-Only	CLIP-VIT	21.7	14.3	25.0	16.6	5.6	3.0	7.0	5.0	N/A
MLP-Base	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	17.6	19.4	21.0	18.7	2.6	6.6	3.8	7.6	N/A
MLP-Roberta	Image+Text	CLIP-VIT	45.2	1.4	45.7	2.4	5.8	3.0	7.0	4.7	N/A
XceptionNet	Image-Only	XceptionNet	16.7	11.3	19.4	10.7	1.3	0.3	1.3	1.3	N/A
XceptionNet	Image-Only	XceptionNet	6.0	7.9	7.4	7.0	1.1	0.1	2.8	1.0	ImageNet
Resnet50	Image-Only	Resnet50	17.8	11.0	24.8	13.4	4.3	33.6	4.3	34.1	N/A
Resnet50	Image-Only	Resnet50	6.0	3.0	5.8	4.0	0.2	0.2	1.1	1.0	ImageNet

Table 6. Percentage of false negatives and false positives in the two categories considered, animate and inanimate objects, on Wikimedia test dataset with images generated with Stable Diffusion or GLIDE.

232 50%, demonstrating a total inability to generalize. The introduction of textual features also does not
233 help to improve classification, and this can also be related to the different nature of captions compared to
234 those in MSCOCO. In fact, from our observations, Wikimedia’s captions can be much less descriptive, so
235 finding inconsistencies between text and image can be more complex.

236 4.3 Error Analysis

237 The structure of the Wikimedia dataset allows us to perform an error analysis by category. As mentioned
238 above, we have predictively categorized the images in this dataset into various categories (e.g., Artist, City,
239 Road, River, Animal, etc) based on the ontologies provided by Wikipedia and the tags associated with
240 each image. They were then further grouped into two macro-categories, namely inanimate and animate
241 objects. Based on these categories, we analyzed the errors committed by the classifiers on the test set.

242 In Table 6, we give an example of the percentage false negative, namely undetected generated images,
243 and percentage false positive, namely wrongly classified real images, made on the Wikimedia test set of
244 trained models. Looking at the false negative results, the models tend to have more difficulty identifying
245 generated images when the image depicts an inanimate object (e.g. buildings, roads, objects, infrastructure,
246 rivers etc) than when it is an image with animate subjects (people, animals etc). In other words, images
247 generated by both models depicting inanimate subjects are more believable and, therefore, more difficult
248 to distinguish from real images. For example, generating a credible person or animal in the eyes of the
249 classifier thus seems to be a more difficult task for the text-to-image systems under consideration. Some

Feature	Description
LENGTH	The length of the caption
ADJ	Number of adjectives (e.g. big, old, green)
ADP	Number of prepositions (e.g. in, to, during)
ADV	Number of adverbs (e.g. very, tomorrow, down)
AUX	Number of auxiliaries (e.g. is, will do, should do)
CCONJ	Number of coordinating conjunctions (e.g. and, or, but)
DET	Number of determiners (e.g. a, an, the)
INTJ	Number of interjections (e.g. psst, ouch, hello)
NOUN	Number of nouns (e.g. girl, cat, air)
NUM	Number of numbers (e.g. 1995, 7, seventy, XXII)
PART	Number of particles (e.g. 's, not)
PRON	Number of pronouns (e.g. I, she, you)
PROPN	Number of proper nouns (e.g. James, USA, NATO)
PUNCT	Number of punctuations (e.g. ., ?, !)
SCONJ	Number of subordinating conjunction (e.g. if, while, that)
SYM	Number of symbols (e.g. @, \$, -)
VERB	Number of verbs (e.g. runs, fly, eat)
X	Number of other type of constructs
SPACE	Number of spaces
STOPS	Number of stop words (e.g. and, by, of)
NON_ALPHA	Number of non-alphabetic words (e.g. 1, 1997, 33)
NAMED_ENTITIES	Number of named entities (London, Gary, EU)

Table 7. Features used for the linguistic analysis conducted with their acronyms.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation values between the linguistic features and the classification provided by an MLP in the image+text setup (CLIP-ViT). The first row refers to the dataset composed of real images and images generated by Stable Diffusion while the second row refers to the dataset with GLIDE images.

250 structures in the human body seem to be particularly challenging to generate such as the hand’s fingers,
 251 increasing the probability of artifact introduction. On the other hand, an inanimate object due to its
 252 variety, can contain anomalies or inconsistencies introduced by generators that could easily be mistaken
 253 for normality or peculiarities of the scene.

254 4.4 Linguistic Analysis

255 To better understand the nature of the errors made by the classifiers, we investigated linguistically the
 256 captioning associated with them in an attempt to understand whether the patterns are influenced by
 257 particular elements in the sentences. The correlation between the correct or incorrect classification of an
 258 image and the linguistic features listed and described in Table 7 was analyzed. These linguistic features
 259 are extracted using a language processing pipeline trained on blogs and web articles taken from SpaCy².
 260 This pipeline can analyze sentences and extract linguistic features from them, such as if a token is a
 261 conjunction, an adjective and so on.

262 Figure 4 shows examples of Pearson correlation between the classification of an MLP trained on
 263 real images and images generated by one of the two methods analyzed (Stable Diffusion and GLIDE)

²<https://spacy.io/>

Figure 5. t-SNE visualization of features extracted using Resnet50 or XceptionNet on 300 fake and 300 pristine images from MSCOCO dataset.

Figure 6. t-SNE visualization of features extracted using CLIP for the visual part and CLIP or RoBERTa for the captions of 300 fake and 300 pristine images from the MSCOCO dataset.

264 and the linguistic features considered. To do so, these were extracted from each caption associated with
 265 the test images, and the correlation between their variation and the classification provided by the model
 266 was derived. As can be seen from the figure, there is no strong correlation between these features and
 267 the classification. It thus appears to be more influenced by the category of the image rather than the
 268 composition of the sentence.

269 4.5 Features Exploration

270 In Figure 5 we visualized the features extracted through Resnet50 and XceptionNet on 300 fake and 300
 271 pristine images randomly selected from the MSCOCO validation set. These features were dimensionally
 272 reduced via PCA and visualized using t-SNE. As can be seen from the plots, the features extracted using
 273 only the pre-trained model of the two networks are not significant at all, causing an important overlap
 274 between pristine and fake classes. After training on the deepfake detection task, on the other hand, the
 275 features, especially of XceptionNet, are extremely good at discriminating between the two classes. Using
 276 these features allows the classification head of these models to easily achieve an incomparable level of
 277 performance since they already are very discriminative.

278 In Figure 6 we show the same visualization but for the experiments where visual features are obtained

279 via CLIP. It can be seen that in these cases, without any kind of fine-tuning on the task, the pristine
280 and fake images features are somewhat more separated even if they still remain rather mixed. This is
281 confirmed both in the image-only setup and in the case where textual features (whether from CLIP or
282 RoBERTa) are used. In this context, the MLP learns to discriminate between fake and pristine images by
283 exploiting the peculiarities of these features without any fine-tuning of the backbones.

284 5 CONCLUSIONS

285 In this study, we conducted some analysis on the detection of content generated by text-to-image systems,
286 particularly Stable Diffusion and GLIDE. We tested several classifiers between MLPs and Convolutional
287 Neural Networks highlighting how classical deep learning models are easily able to distinguish images
288 generated with these systems when they have seen examples of them in the training set, in particular when
289 they conducted some pretraining on large datasets. By screening their generalization ability, however, they
290 are rarely able to identify images generated by methods other than those used to construct the training set
291 thus highlighting an important issue for these systems to be adopted in the real world. In that context,
292 the introduction of textual features extracted from the images' captions can be helpful in some cases
293 helping the detectors to identify inconsistencies between text and image. An analysis of the correlation
294 between the credibility of the generated images and the category to which they belong as well as the
295 composition of the caption associated with them was also conducted. From our experiments, the images
296 generated by both the considered generators are more credible when they depict inanimate objects and
297 thus result in greater error on the part of the classifiers. Conversely, images depicting people, animals,
298 or animate subjects in general are easier to identify. In addition, there does not appear to be a strong
299 correlation between the linguistic composition of the sentence and the classification ability of the models.
300 Some future works will include the exploration of different generators, datasets, and architectures and the
301 development of new ideas to boost the generalization capabilities of the detectors. In this direction we
302 could try to train models using a reduced set of data from multiple generators in an attempt to find out
303 what amount and type of images generated by a given method are necessary to achieve optimal detection
304 performance.

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